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1. Introduction

Novel services offered by research infrastructures (RIs) were developed in Work Package (WP) 6, aiming to attract new users beyond the research community and to enhance the overall use and capacity of existing atmospheric RIs by exploring innovative access modalities. To open access to new users, several innovative transnational access (TNA) modalities were developed specifically for three target groups: (1) international stakeholders, (2) innovators in technology, and (3) public authorities. From task (T) 6.1, it was concluded that the new TNA modalities should be co-designed with the stakeholders of interest to effectively respond to the requirements and evolving needs of the users (Wenger 2022). The implemented services and established liaisons are summarised in the deliverables (D) of D6.2 for international stakeholders (Nicolae, Petracca Altieri, and Wenger 2023), D6.3, for innovators in technology (Rivier et al. 2023), and of D6.4, for public authorities (Athanasopoulou 2023). A brief overview of the project updates complementing these deliverables can be found in the recently submitted Milestone (MS) 24 (Fuchs et al. 2025).

In order to evaluate the newly introduced services, surveys were issued to each group of users. In this report, the results and analysis of the user feedback is evaluated. Firstly, the newly offered services tailored to the three different types of users (international stakeholders, innovators in technology, public authorities) are briefly introduced. A detailed description and a summary of these pilot projects can be found in the corresponding deliverables (Athanasopoulou 2023; Nicolae, Petracca Altieri, and Wenger 2023; Rivier et al. 2023;) and milestone (Fuchs et al. 2025). Secondly, the metrics to evaluate the collected user feedback in each WP6 task and the obtained results are presented. At the end, the results are discussed, and the effectiveness of the pilot projects is assessed. The report concludes with recommendations for future optimised TNA programs.

2. Overview of TNA pilots

Three TNA pilot projects were initiated in WP6 addressing specific needs and requirements by international stakeholders (T6.2), innovators in technology (T6.3), and public authorities (T6.4). For each pilot, one project was tested, and its attractiveness towards the stakeholders appeared promising. Table 1 **Error! Reference source not found.** summarises the different pilot projects and partners. Details on the approaches are discussed in the following sections.

Table 1. Overview of the different TNA pilots, involved stakeholders, and the approaches on how to engage the stakeholders. The table is adapted from MS24 (Fuchs et al. 2025).

WP6 Tasks	6.2	6.3	6.4
Target users	International stakeholders	Innovators in technology	Public authorities
Lead beneficiary	INOE	CNRS	NOA
Involved stakeholders	ESA, EUMETSAT	Private sector	Facility providers of ACTRIS, ICLEI-EU ¹ network members, RI-URBANS ² , ATMO ACCESS
Approach	Satellite Cal/Val	Atmobox	Workshop on the ambient AQ directive

2.1 TNA pilot for international stakeholders (task 6.2)

The goal of task 6.2 was to explore new TNA modalities that are tailored to requirements and needs of international stakeholders. In total, three pilot projects were designed and implemented in collaboration with the European Space Agency (ESA) and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). Figure 1 summarises the overall process from the definition of pilot projects to their implementation. The process was adapted from the standard TNA approach (Petraçca Altieri et al. 2021), however allowed flexible access modalities. In contrast to the standard TNA procedure, the interaction of ATMO-ACCESS with the users is much more intense. In a first step, the needs of international stakeholders, focusing on ESA, EUMETSAT, Copernicus, and EEA³, were identified by the working group (WG) comprising 19 experts, and subsequently discussed with the stakeholders. International stakeholders, which were interested in recurring physical, remote, and/or virtual access to multiple ATMO-ACCESS facilities at the same time, could submit a concept note in a third step, which was then evaluated by independent experts, as it is handled with applications of standard TNA calls. Unlike the standard TNA procedure, the concept notes and the realisation

¹ ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability (known as ICLEI) is a global network working with more than 2500 local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development.

² RI-URBANS - Research Infrastructures Services Reinforcing Air Quality Monitoring Capacities in European Urban & Industrial AreaS: Green Deal H2020 EU Project

³ EEA – European Environment Agency

of the project implementations into the TNA program were further developed in the co-design phase, involving stakeholders (ESA and EUMETSAT), ATMO-ACCESS, and facility providers. Subsequently, the revised concept notes were evaluated a second time and the final “Go”/“No go” decision of the implementation of the projects into the TNA was discussed between reviewers, WP6 members, the strategic TNA/VA board, the project coordination, and the TNA management team.

In total, three Cal/Val projects were submitted in the process and eventually implemented in the TNA, targeting the

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the process for defining the pilot projects and implementation plans. The figure is adapted from Nicolae, Petracca Altieri, and Wenger (2023).

following satellite missions: (1) EUMETSAT Aerosol, (2) EUMETSAT Clouds, and (3) ESA EarthCARE. Table 2 gives an overview of the main activities of the TNA pilot projects. While the projects in collaboration with EUMETSAT require remote and virtual access to the Data Centre, the ESA EarthCARE project additionally involves physical access to the ACTRIS aerosol and cloud remote sensing facilities.

Table 2. Overview of the implemented pilot projects and the main TNA activities.

Pilot project	Main activities
EUMETSAT Aerosol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provision of aerosol parameters, among others needed for EUMETSAT instrumentation, and of ACTRIS products from all available ground stations with specific requirements and a specific format - Reprocessing of historical data to generate required format and to meet requirements needed
EUMETSAT Clouds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provision of cloud parameters and of ACTRIS-Cloudnet products from all available ground stations with specific requirements and a specific format

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reprocessing of historical data to generate required format and to meet requirements needed
ESA EarthCARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation of fast data delivery and of validation - Pre-launch network rehearsal campaign and post-launch validation with Near Real Time data delivery - Intercalibration with other networks and ESA's reference instruments

2.2 TNA pilot for innovators in technology (task 6.3)

In task 6.3, new TNA modalities were investigated with a special focus on innovators in technology. Based direct interactions with the private sectors and lessons learnt from previous TNA activities involving companies, sector-specific needs were identified, leading to the launch of a tailored pilot project: the Atmobox (Figure 2). The Atmobox is a modular platform hosting up to eight mid- to low-cost sensors. Two services were offered from March 2024: (1) testing sensors against reference instruments and (2) using the Atmobox for measuring greenhouse gases and air quality parameters on a campaign basis.

For the service (1), the testing of the sensors against the reference instruments was entirely supported by the ATC Metrology Lab (Mlab) of the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) network, providing technical, scientific, and administrative support. From the beginning of 2025, originally designed for ICOS greenhouse gas measurements, Atmoboxes are also being developed at the ACTRIS Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas) at the Institute Mines Telecom (IMT), extending their use to reactive trace gases. Remote scientific and technical support in addition to training is also offered as part of the service (2).

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the process for developing and implementing the pilot project "Atmobox". The Atmobox which can be equipped with up to eight sensors. Two services are offered: Testing the sensors against reference instruments, as shown, or using the Atmo box in field campaigns. The figure is taken from(Fuchs et. al. 2025).

The new services are accessible via TNA to the ICOS-ATC facility. Generally, the TNA process for the private sector follows the standard procedure, however, some specific measures were applied, in particular to streamline the process:

- Flexible timescale for application (no deadline to the TNA call)
- Additional review criterion introduced, related to the innovation potential, expected impact on economy and potential technological and/or market developments
- Shortened evaluation process (2-3 weeks)

Despite including the Atmobox in both the private sector call and the last general call for access, it has not been booked by the intended stakeholders of interest (innovators in technology). Instead, the Atmobox has primarily been used in measurement campaigns in urban areas in France. Due to the missing user feedback for the Atmobox, this specific pilot project cannot be evaluated in detail. Instead, feedback from innovators in technology who successfully accessed ATMO-ACCESS services through other TNA calls has been considered. Despite this, the Atmobox remains a promising service with potential for future uptake once awareness and engagement among the target stakeholders increase.

2.3 TNA pilot for public authorities (T6.4)

The interaction among public authority (PA) representatives, facility providers, and the coordination team was strengthened through a series of engagement activities (Table 3). The workflow of the task is shown in Figure 3. Through these activities, awareness of ATMO-ACCESS and of the concept of TNAs was raised, while user needs, service and access requirements and provider availabilities and capacities were explored, identified, and assessed. As a tangible outcome, the pilot TNA opportunity for public authorities took the form of a set of training webinars, supporting the instrumentation and measurements of the pollutants newly incorporated into the framework of the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive.

Figure 3. The workflow of T6.4. Rectangles in blue indicate processes which were supported by several modes and types of interaction (in grey). Rectangles in green indicate the intermediate and final outputs. The figure is taken from Athanasopoulou (2023).

Table 3. List of networks approached within the activities of T6.4. The table is adopted from Athanasopoulou (2023).

No	Network	Logo / Website	Short Description
1	ACTRIS members and stakeholders	 https://www.actris.eu/actris-stakeholders	A pan-European research infrastructure producing high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents. Its stakeholders originate -among others- from public services, from countries inside and outside Europe.
2	ICLEI-EU network	 https://iclei-europe.org/our-members/	ICLEI Europe's Members represent local governments and governmental associations
3	RI-URBANS stakeholders	 https://riurbans.eu/project/#stakeholders	The project has a Stakeholders Board to intensify an optimised collaboration between the beneficiaries representing AQMNs and European RIs (notably ACTRIS and IAGOS) at the local, national and European levels.
4	Facility providers	 https://www.atmo-access.eu/facilities/	A network of European atmospheric research facilities, which provide access to -among others- the public sector in the framework of ATMO-ACCESS

3. Assessment and Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation of the TNA pilot projects is based on user feedback collected within the scope of the different pilot projects. An overview of the questionnaires and surveys which form the basis for the analysis is shown in Table 4. In total, eight questionnaires were issued. For the evaluation of the TNA pilot projects, only the feedback questionnaires about the final pilot project are evaluated in this deliverable (questionnaires 2 and 3 for T6.2, questionnaire 4 for T6.3, and questionnaire 8 for T6.4). Questionnaires 1, 5, 6, and 7 were already evaluated in the respective deliverables (Wenger 2022; Nicolae et. al. 2023; Rivier et. al. 2023; Athanasopoulou 2023).

Within the scope of T6.2, two feedback rounds were conducted during implementation of access, each corresponding to a distinct phase of the project implementation. The first round, held in February 2024, focused on the preparatory stage, including the development and optimisation of the tailored services (e.g., tools, rehearsal campaigns) (questionnaire 2, Table 4). The second round, conducted in March 2025, targeted more advanced stages such as the optimisation of quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC), the execution of calibration and Cal/Val campaigns, and the validation of resulting products (questionnaire 3, Table 4). This two-phase structure enabled the collection of feedback across both the optimised implementation and operational dimensions of the pilot, offering a more comprehensive understanding of stakeholder perceptions and the evolution of their experiences over time. The online survey was issued to the involved users (ESA, EUMETSAT) and access providers, and in total 51 responses were collected, with 25 and 26 participants in the first and second round, respectively. Most of the participants were access providers including 39 ATMO-ACCESS beneficiaries. In the first survey (questionnaire 2, Table 4), four of the 25 participants were stakeholders, while only one stakeholder representative participated in the second survey (questionnaire 3, Table 4). Since the participation in the surveys was anonymous, the distribution of the votes of the two stakeholders ESA and EUMETSAT is unclear as is the identity of the providers. It should be noted that the international stakeholders' projects involved two large entities, thus the number of responses to the surveys was expected to be much less than the ones from the providers, especially since the surveys were only distributed within the involved parties. Since both the stakeholders and the access providers were strongly involved in the design of the pilot project and its implementation, the feedback of task 6.2 is still highly valuable.

For the TNA pilot project for innovators in technology (T6.3) no pilot-specific questionnaire was issued since the private sector have not yet shown any interest in the services of the Atmobox. Therefore, the general TNA user feedback from the private sector is considered (questionnaire 4, Table 4). The general TNA user feedback comprises feedback from TNA activities in all TNA

calls, except the 4th and 6th calls, which did not involve any projects from private companies. The majority of the TNA projects evaluated in this report was part of the continuously open private sector TNA call (52%) or of the first three general TNA calls (41%). A first evaluation was already performed in D6.3 (Rivier et. al. 2023) covering a total of 23 TNA applications which were granted to private companies up to the end of 2024. This report presents an updated evaluation, including 46 TNAs activities performed by 31 companies. Detailed feedback was given by 16 companies. Based on the title of the TNA projects, 13 of the 46 TNA projects were strongly coupled to innovation with the aim of testing, evaluating or intercomparing novel instrumentation. Additional 22 TNA projects were dedicated to applying specific atmospheric instrumentation. The remaining 11 TNA projects focused on research topics, which does not necessarily exclude an involvement of novel instrumentation.

User feedback for the TNA pilot project for public authorities was collected during and after each of the two training webinars (questionnaire 8, Table 4). An online poll was accessible during and after the webinars while the final survey was issued after the second training webinar. The first (UFP and PNSD) and second (VOCs, PM, OP, and BC) training webinars³ were attended by 100 and 125 people, respectively. Responses from 164 people were received in total. The high number of participants in this pilot activity was likely achieved by the targeted promotion of this ATMO-ACCESS activity, not only within the already engaged communities but also through additional newsletters (e.g., WHO Breathlife2030). It is worth noting that most registered people were activated through e-mails (by the RIs, the WHO or colleagues). In addition to the final survey and the online poll, feedback from the stakeholder workshop (questionnaire 1, Table 4) is evaluated and compared to the feedback from the training webinars. The event targeting the ICLEI-EU members cannot support any conclusions and recommendations, due to the limited feedback from this survey.

All questionnaires issued contained mainly multiple-choice questions, partly allowing multiple answers. For open-text questions, i.e. no multiple-choice questions, the responses were sorted into groups and lumped. If depicted, the relative participation was derived from normalising the number of votes to the number of voting persons.

³ While the first webinar focused on the guidance and monitoring of ultra-fine particles (UFP) and the particle number size distribution (PNSD), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), the speciation of particulate matter (PM), the oxidative potential (OP) of atmospheric particles, and black carbon (BC) were discussed in the second webinar.

Figure 4. Metrics for evaluating the user feedback collected in tasks 6.2 to 6.4.

As part of WP2 (Stachlewska, Szczepanik, and Dubost 2024), key-performance indicators (KPIs) were developed which were used as starting point for analysing the user feedback. Additional performance indicators were developed which are tailored to the different tasks and which can be extracted from the collected user feedback (Figure 4). In a first step, each task is evaluated separately with regard to the specific KPIs, to assess the success of the different pilot projects. Not all the specific KPIs could be extracted from every task-specific feedback making a direct comparison of the different pilot projects challenging. Therefore, general KPIs were developed comparing the pilot projects qualitatively, to evaluate the pilot projects and their possible role in future.

Table 4. Questionnaires issued in the frame of ATMO-ACCESS WP6. Questionnaires highlighted in yellow form the basis of the evaluation of the TNA pilot projects. In orange questionnaires are highlighted which were partly analysed within the scope of this report. The table is adapted from Fuchs et al. (2025).

No	Title	In the frame of T6.x	Stakeholders addressed	Goal(s)	Number of participants (stakeholders)	Issue date
1	"Questionnaire for providers and users"	T6.2, T6.3, T6.4	Users (public sector) and Providers (ATMO-ACCESS RI community)	Co-design of the pilot access of PAs to RIs	160 ()	27/10/2021
2	"Questionnaire to collect recommendations"	T6.2	ESA, EUMETSAT (stakeholders), access providers	Feedback and recommendations at mid-term of pilots' implementation	25 (4)	13/03/2024
3	"Questionnaire to collect recommendations"	T6.2	ESA, EUMETSAT (stakeholders), access providers	Feedback and recommendations at end of pilots' implementation	26 (1)	01/03/2025
4	"Private sector user feedback"	T6.3	Private sector (stakeholders)	Feedback on the TNA application and the services provided	25/46 ^a	2021-2025
5	"Questionnaire for access providers"	T6.4	Facility providers: Representatives from the RIs of ATMO-ACCESS	Initial interest of access providers, input on the nature of the pilot	30 (0)	23/07-27/-8/08/2021
6	"Questionnaire to collect user needs"	T6.4	Public authorities (stakeholders)	Co-design of the pilot access of RIs by PAs	5 (5)	16/03/2023

7	"Questionnaire to collect provider capacities"	T6.4	Facility providers: Representatives from the RIs of ATMO-ACCESS	Preferences/availability of facility reps. For access by PAs	8 (0)	11/2023
8	"Questionnaire to collect recommendations"	T6.4	Public authorities (stakeholders)	Evaluation and sustainability of T6.4	164 ^b (≥ 48) ^c	04/10/- 30/11/2024

^a All participants were stakeholders. Specific user feedback is available for 16 users. General information about the TNA users is available for all 46 accessing enterprises.

^b The dissemination of the events was intensive, not only through the ATMO-ACCESS list (RI-Urbans contacts included), but also through the WHO Breathlife2030 newsletter.

^d A lower limit is given since only 48 participants responded to the question about their profession.

4. Results

4.1 International stakeholders

In the evaluation of the user feedback from international stakeholders' survey their responses are highlighted with stripes in the graphs to better distinguish them (Section 3). Nevertheless, the overall responses will be mainly discussed from the first round, due to the lower number of international stakeholders participating in the second survey.

Figure 5. Challenges for international stakeholders to access the classic TNA program.

The analysis of barriers preventing international stakeholders from accessing TNA programs in their classical form reveals several key insights (Figure 5). The most frequently cited reason by the international stakeholders and by the access providers across both rounds was a lack of awareness of the opportunity, with on average 55% of the respondents in both rounds identifying this as the main issue. Bureaucracy was also considered a significant obstacle, mentioned by 52% and 35% of all respondents in the first and second round, respectively, indicating that this perception diminished over time, likely due to improved coordination during the implementation phase. Other barriers such as trans-national constraints and the "single-facility" approach were cited by 38% of the respondents on average, underscoring the preference among international stakeholders for more flexible, multi-facility access models. In particular, the persistent concern over the single-facility model suggests a misalignment between classical TNA structures and the operational needs of international users, who often require access across multiple sites or services. Interestingly, the barrier related to conceptual and terminological misunderstanding decreased in round two (selected by 48% and 31% of the participants in the first and second round, respectively), reflecting a positive learning curve

among stakeholders as they became more familiar with the vocabulary and framework of the program. The competitive nature of the access process, while initially a minor concern, became even less significant in the second round (dropping from 20 % to 8 %), suggesting growing clarity or increased confidence in the fairness and transparency of the selection process.

What are the main benefits of the ATMO-ACCESS pilot projects for international stakeholders, from your perspective?

Figure 6. Main benefits of the TNA pilot project for international stakeholders.

In comparison with the standard TNA program, the stakeholders and access providers particularly valued the involvement of many and diverse facilities and expertise in the dedicated TNA pilot project, which was cited by more than 80% and 55% of the respondents in the first and second round, respectively, confirming its centrality to stakeholder engagement (Figure 6). Similarly, coordination through the research infrastructure and direct stakeholder involvement in planning and reporting were equally recognised by 3 out of 4 and 1 out of 1 international stakeholders in the first and second round, respectively, and by more than 50% of all respondents in both rounds.

Between the two rounds, the value for money saw notable increases in appreciation which is also valid for the transparency of the whole process and the combination of various access modalities when comparing the distribution of the votes, reflecting the stakeholders' enhanced understanding and positive reception of the program's flexibility and efficiency. Conversely, the comparison of the distribution of votes for round one and two shows that elements such as the reduced bureaucracy, the guidance in effort estimation and in the implementation of the activities, and the flexibility during implementation were less cited in round two, suggesting that

these aspects became less critical once procedural tools and structures were fully in place, highlighting the importance of providing guidance and support early in the process. Overall, the strongest identified benefits of the TNA pilot project for international stakeholders recognised by the providers and especially by the international stakeholders in the second round are the coordination, co-design, involvement of many expertise and access modalities, emphasising the need for continuous collaboration and adjustments of the TNA framework for these users.

Weaknesses of the TNA pilot project for international stakeholders include the duration of the pilot in relation to the Cal/Val (Calibration/Validation) needs with a sharp increase in concern from approximately 53% of the access providers in round one to more than 80% in round two (Figure 7). This substantial rise reflects a growing dissatisfaction with the time limitations of the pilot which however was further constrained due to the nearly two-month delay of EarthCARE’s launch, leading to a duration of the pilot of four instead of six months. By contrast, criticism related to the number of meetings and reports dropped from around 32% to 12%, indicating that either procedural improvements were made during the implementation or stakeholders’ familiarity with the process increased over time. Even though the complexity of the selection process was less criticised in the second round the participating international stakeholders still feel the selection process to be too long and complicated. Similarly, the high workload relative to resources was criticised by the facility providers.

Figure 7. Feedback on the dedicated TNA pilot project for international stakeholders.

The overall responses to the TNA pilot project reveal a generally positive outlook, with over 90% of respondents across both rounds indicating willingness to participate again, either with some optimisations, such as e.g., the time limitation, or because the pilots have demonstrated their utility (Figure 7). In the first round, more than 50% of the respondents selected “Yes, the pilots have demonstrated their utility” compared to just under 45% in the second round. Conversely,

the proportion selecting “Maybe, with some optimisations” increased slightly in round two reaching just over 50%. This shift suggests a moderate decline in optimism, as reflected in the comments, with stakeholders increasingly acknowledging the value of the project but also highlighting the need for adjustments. Negative responses remained low in both rounds: less than 5% of participants felt that either the results did not justify the effort or that the funding was insufficient.

Participants of the surveys were also asked whether the European Commission (EC) should consider establishing dedicated TNA programs for international stakeholders and RIs (Figure 8). The responses overwhelmingly indicate that EC support is both needed and advisable, confirming the general opinion expressed in stakeholder comments. The most frequently selected option was “Yes, EC support is needed because funds are limited at the side of the RIs and of the stakeholder”, with about 60% of the respondents in round two choosing this response—an increase from approximately 33% in round one. This notable rise suggests a growing concern regarding financial constraints faced by both access providers and international users, which became more pressing than the perceived impact of such programs. In particular financial support for the harmonisation of the data access was desired by a stakeholder in the second round. Conversely, the share of respondents who selected “Yes, EC should develop such a program in order to maximise the impact of the RIs (cascade effect)” decreased from almost 60% in round one to just over 30% in round two. This shift implies that although stakeholders continue to value the strategic benefits of cascading impacts across the research landscape, immediate funding limitations at provider level have become the more urgent issue. The two remaining options—suggesting that RIs or stakeholders could independently manage and fund such programs—received very limited support, remaining below 10% of total responses across both rounds, indicating that independent efforts are not considered a viable or sufficient solution.

Figure 8. Feedback on how a dedicated TNA program for international stakeholders would look like.

The survey results identify a clear set of stakeholder priorities for the design of a potential dedicated TNA program targeting international stakeholders and RIs (Figure 8). The most frequently cited features, consistent across both rounds, include a simplified process for accessing RI facilities, co-design of the projects between stakeholders and providers (each selected by about 80% of the respondents in round one and approximately 50% in round two), and co-ordination between stakeholders and RIs (selected by about 60% of the respondents in round one and approximately 50% in round two). These elements were described in stakeholder feedback as essential to improving usability, inclusivity, and alignment with user needs. Similarly, co-funding mechanisms involving the EC, stakeholders, and providers were considered critical by 67% and 43% of the respondents in round one and two, respectively, indicating sustained support for shared financial responsibility across parties.

While core structural features remained relatively stable across both rounds, there was a notable increase in the perceived importance of combined access modalities and open access to results. For instance, the relative importance of the combined access modalities increased in round two, as did open access to results, which increased from under 10% to approximately 30%. These shifts suggest that stakeholders do not only value strategic collaboration and procedural efficiency but are also increasingly attentive to the scientific output and long-term visibility of the results generated through TNA programs.

4.2 Innovators in technology

To evaluate TNA modalities for innovators in technology, the general user feedback of TNA users from the private sector was evaluated. Feedback from in total 46 TNA projects was evaluated which were performed mainly in the first three general TNA calls and in the private sector call (Figure 9). A strong increase in projects within the scope of the private sector TNA call demonstrates the effectiveness of attracting the private sector via an optimised TNA concept.

Figure 9. Number of projects granted for private companies in the different TNA calls.

Companies participating in the TNA program were mainly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), while only 19% of the companies were other industrial and/or profit-oriented private organisations. The majority, namely 77.5%, of the companies specialise in Earth and environmental sciences (ENV-ATMO, ENV-ECOBIO) followed by the engineering and technology sector (16% contribution, ENG-TECH, Figure 10). Other scientific fields of activity such as physics (PHY) and chemistry (CHEM) are only represented by one company each (i.e. 3.2% contribution). 29 of the 31 institutions are from Europe, with France, Germany, and the Netherlands making up about 50% of the head offices (Figure 10), highlighting the need to promote the TNA program in other countries. The two non-European institutions are located in the United States. In general, the private companies took notice of the TNA program through recommendations from colleagues or personal contacts (54%), information desks at events (23%) such as the European Aerosol Conference (EAC), the websites of ATMO-ACCESS or specific RIs (15%), or via direct mailing from the RIs (8%).

Figure 10. The field of activity (left) and the country of the head office for the 31 companies accessing TNA in ATMO-ACCESS (right).

23 of the 31 companies participated for the first time in the TNA program, while four companies accessed the ATMO-ACCESS RIs twice and three companies participated three times (Figure 11), emphasising the strong interest of the private sector in accessing RI services. The highest amount of TNA applications, with six in total, was granted to a company from Slovenia who accessed 5 different facilities. Services requested by the private sector included to a large extent research and/or innovation services (~ 70% contribution) involving the testing of new products, methods, or systems leading to a better understanding of performance. Technical services such as calibrations or quality control of systems made up 28% of the 46 TNA activities, whereas training services such as thematic courses were only in demand by one company, i.e. 2% of the TNA awards (Figure 11). Research infrastructures were mainly accessed physically or in a combination of physical and remote.

Figure 11. The number of TNAs conducted by the private companies (left) and the type of access of the different TNAs sorted by the requested service (right).

Only four of the 46 TNAs were done completely remotely, highlighting that the private sector view physical access to atmospheric RI facilities as highly valuable (Figure 11). While research and/or innovation services preferred a combined access, technical and training services preferred physical access. Access to observation platforms was most popular (65% contribution) followed by central laboratories and simulation chamber facilities (11% each).

Figure 12. User satisfaction for the ATMO-ACCESS (left) and facility (middle) services as well as the overall TNA experience (right).

Overall, there has been good feedback from the private companies on the TNA activities (Figure 12 and Figure 13). In particular, the experience and on-site support provided by the facilities was appreciated and was rated with 4.8 out of 5 on average (Figure 12). The unique infrastructure, the collaboration and knowledge share between the private and the research sector, and the demonstration, evaluation, and improvement of instruments were highlighted as beneficial from the TNA program (Figure 13). A rating of 4.4 out of 5 was given to the TNA process itself. The complexity of the application and the quantity of the post-access documentation was rated low with 3.8 and 3.4 out of 5, respectively.

Figure 13. Benefits of the TNA for the companies (left) and suggestions for future ATMO-ACCESS services addressing the private sector (right). The amount of bureaucracy and the missing transparency on the documents needed for the TNA was also criticised and desired to be improved (Figure 13). Small companies feel the effort needed for the documentation and the application is too much compared to the ATMO-ACCESS funding. Without the ATMO-ACCESS funding, 72% of the companies would not have been able to access the RIs as they have not been able to cover the travel costs, a possible user fee or the access in general (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Feedback on the ATMO-ACCESS funding from the private sector.

4.3 Public authorities

In total, 202 people registered for the training webinars, of which 147 attended (Figure 15).

In the two webinars, five facility providers were involved discussing the new air quality metrics in 139 minutes (Figure 15). About 25% of the respondents of the surveys participated in the co-design working group meetings of T6.4 (Figure 15). For 33% of the respondents, the webinars were the first ATMO-ACCESS activity they had ever attended, which is in alignment to the small number of participants in the engagement events of T6.4. In order to explore this further, a

targeted question was asked during the webinars, which revealed that the majority (73%) of the 60 newcomers to the two webinars did not know about the preceding T6.4 events or had time constraints (13%, Figure 15). The remaining 30 people, familiar with ATMO-ACCESS activities, have appreciated the collaborative environment (50 %) and the direct involvement of the PAs in the planning (45%).

Figure 15. Statistics of the training webinars (left) and reasons for/against the participation at the co-design working group meetings (right).

Overall, people from 47 countries participated in the webinars with about 75% being from Europe, with Spain, Italy, Germany, and France making up a third overall (Figure 16). The remaining participants were from Asia (15%), Africa (7%), and South America (3%). 50% to 60% of the respondents represented a public authority, of which 60% represented an environmental agency and 19% represented a regional government (Figure 16). Other public authorities involved national institutions (8%), health agencies (4%), and research councils (2%).

Figure 16. Origin (left) and professional field (right) of participants of the webinars for RI-URBANS stakeholders.

As one of the goals of the interaction with the PAs is to make TNA to RIs both attractive and sustainable, some of the questions wanted to explore the reasons behind the limited access of the facilities by representatives from the public sector in the past (Figure 17). The lack of awareness about the TNA programs and/or about their concept has been the main reason that the majority of the 92 public authorities present in the webinars (for 70% of the respondents) was benefiting from the knowledge and expertise of the European (ATMO-ACCESS) RIs outside of their country for the first time. In addition, technical circumstances such as bureaucracy, the limited budget, the inflexible application periods, as well as the access to only trans-national facilities were criticised by 25% to 50% of the participants. Further aspects with contributions less than 25% include the competition with other applicants, language issues, and the access to one single facility. The most favourable service for the PAs having participated in the activities of T6.4 seems to be the (fast track) access to air quality monitoring data (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Challenges for public authorities to access research infrastructures (left) and emerging needs of PAs with respect to RIs (right).

Instrumental services are preferred by 36% of the PAs attending the stakeholder workshop, while interest in source apportionment was also declared (by 46% and 13% of the PAs attending the stakeholder workshop and the training webinars, respectively).

Although the above needs were the most favorable according to the representatives present in the engagement events, national research facilities located within the country should be more suitable institutions for providing, e.g. real-time local data compared to trans-national research facilities. The decision to cover the need for support for guidelines was a strategic one, especially given its timeliness with the EC AQ Directive being under revision and about to come into effect. In addition, this support was not only explicitly identified as a user need, but also relevant to other aspects, like training in measurements and instrumentation or calibration techniques. Given the transnational character of access within ATMO-ACCESS, the obligatory

and geographical dimensions of the Directive, and the limited expertise in measuring emerging pollutants addressed in the webinar, this activity ultimately constituted a successful TNA pilot.

To gain insight on public authorities' needs in terms of access to atmospheric RIs, several questions about the TNA were asked for at the end of each webinar. The need for the sustainability of TNA activities is reflected by the fact that 37% to 52% of the respondents expressed a desire for additional support by the European Commission (EC, Figure 18). A simplified process for accessing the RIs and the co-funding of the TNA was supported by 64% of the participants. On average 41% of the participants welcomed co-design of the projects, combined access modalities and an open access to the results. 24% of the attendees were interested in combined access to facilities, involving more than one facility. Besides, 6 out of 16 participants emphasise the visibility and accessibility of RIs for PAs, especially for non-European and developing countries.

Figure 18. Feedback of PAs participating in the final survey of the TNA webinars on a possible future TNA program dedicated to PAs.

At the end of the survey, feedback on the two training webinars was requested (Figure 19 and Figure 20). 75% of the participants appreciated the online format of the webinars and the involvement of experts from multiple facilities and countries (Figure 19). Furthermore, the direct interaction with the experts was welcome, as well as the discussion of critical issues in an open and no-cost format. For future webinars, participants expressed a preference to discuss specific pollutants in shorter sessions (less than 1.5 hours), and also requested access to the webinar materials (Figure 19). These needs are already partly covered, as the webinar videos webinars are split by pollutant and made publicly available on the ATMO-ACCESS youtube channel. Although the TNA activity included audience questions, a continuous interaction was suggested. Some requested the use of everyday rather than scientific language, while the need for a sustained interaction of the public authorities with the European research community was highlighted, particularly to discuss trends related to air quality measures.

Figure 19. Benefits from the TNA training webinars (left) and suggestions for future webinars (right).

Overall, the rating of the user satisfaction of the TNA webinars is very positive (Figure 20). On a scale of 0 to 5, 50% of the participants gave 5 points and an average rating of 4.3 was achieved.

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Figure 20. User satisfaction with regard to the two TNA (training) webinars.

4.4 Pilot projects in comparison

For assessing the overall potential of the different pilot projects, the pilot projects are evaluated according to the general KPIs (Table 5). The comparison is qualitative as a quantitative approach is not possible due to the different design of the surveys. For task 6.3, both the Atmobox as well as the TNA projects granted to private companies are assessed.

The successful outcome of most of the pilot projects (Sections 4.1 to 4.3) already emphasises the attractiveness of the offered pilot projects to the stakeholders. Stakeholders of all kinds were mainly attracted by the collaboration with the RIs and their expertise. International stakeholders (ESA, EUTMETSAT) appreciated in addition the joint design and coordination of the Cal/Val project together with the RIs. A concern of involved parties of T6.2 (stakeholders and

access providers) and of few private companies accessing the RIs was however the lack of resources and at the same time the large amount of effort needed for realising the TNA projects.

Since Cal/Val projects of satellite missions are needed on a long-term basis, the pilot project of T6.2 has a large access potential. Also, the high participation of private companies particularly in the private-sector TNA call, and the multiple accesses by 25% of companies to RIs demonstrate the effectiveness of targeted TNA calls in attracting the private sector, highlighting their potential to support sustained engagement if adequate sources and institutional backing are provided. The future potential of the pilot project for public authorities is at the present time challenging to judge. A high participation was observed for the two webinars, however whether this trend is perpetuated in future is uncertain and might only persist either by constantly attracting new stakeholders or by adapting the topics of the webinars to possibly changing needs of the recurring participants. These engagement events may however lead to possible future TNA projects. The future uptake of the Atmobox by the private sector needs to be demonstrated, as it has not yet attracted interest from innovators in technology.

The Atmobox and the private-sector TNA call have been successfully implemented in the TNA program. However, an optimisation of the TNA program, involving reduced bureaucracy and an improved transparency on the documents needed, is required to attract a wider range of international stakeholders and innovators in technology on the long term.

In future, training events, such as performed in T6.4, could be accessible via the TNA and also the virtual access (VA). In contrast, the long-term access needed for the Cal/Val project is not compatible with the standard TNA which is designed to provide only short-term access. Thus, an adaption of the standard TNA program is needed for Cal/Val projects, allowing long-term access of multiple RIs at the same time.

Table 5. Qualitative evaluation of the different pilot projects based on the general key-performance indicators (KPIs, Figure 4).

General KPIs	Pilot projects			
	Cal/Val (T6.2)	Atmobox (T6.3)	Attracting private companies	Webinars (T6.4)
Attractiveness to stakeholders	High - Involvement of many and diverse RIs and expertise - Co-design and coordination through RI and stakeholders		High - Access to RI and expertise - Demonstration of instrumentation - But: Small companies may lack the resources	High - Involvement of experts from multiple facilities and countries - Getting into contact with ATMO-ACCESS
Potential of access modalities	High Long-term project	- Cannot be judged due to missing feedback	High Multiple companies applied more than once for TNA	Medium - Constantly high participation can only be achieved by constantly attracting new stakeholders or by evolving services adapted to possibly changing needs of the stakeholders May lead to future TNA projects
Feasibility with current TNA concept	Low - Current TNA concept is not meant for long-term projects - Further optimisations requested	High Already implemented in TNA to the ICOS-ATC facility	High - Private-sector call already implemented - Further optimisations requested	High Fits into the TNA as well as the virtual access (VA) program

5 Discussion

User feedback was collected in the different tasks allowing to evaluate the success and the effectiveness of the three different TNA pilot projects. Overall, the pilot projects of tasks 6.2 and 6.4 were successful. Stakeholders of interest were attracted by all pilot projects, except for the pilot project of T6.3 which was implemented only few months before the end of the pilot projects. Instead, the private-sector TNA call drew many innovators in technology. The potential of the evaluated projects, in particular of the Cal/Val pilot project and the private-sector TNA call is promising, however optimisations of the current TNA concept are needed, as discussed below.

Overall, the TNA pilot project for international stakeholders was successful in demonstrating its relevance and usefulness, even if logistical and structural challenges were present. International stakeholders place significant value on multi-facility engagement, clear coordination mechanisms via RIs, and being actively involved in the process, particularly when such involvement is embedded in a well-supported and transparent operational framework. As the pilot matured, the shift in emphasis from procedural support to strategic integration suggests a successful transition towards a more stakeholder-oriented access model. In this context, the findings clearly point to the need for future access programs to adopt longer timeframes in order to align with stakeholders' scientific timelines, particularly those involving calibration and validation activities. Addressing this limitation will be critical for improving the perceived value and impact of transnational access initiatives. Overall, while the second round of feedback identifies evenly distributed categories of benefits, the findings indicate strong support for future iterations of similar projects, provided that key areas—particularly project duration and administrative structure—are further optimised. The results confirm that stakeholders recognise the strategic value of transnational access frameworks, but expect continuous improvement based on pilot-phase learnings.

Since the pilot project of task 6.3, the Atmobox, did not attract any innovator in technology within the time frame of the pilots, the TNA projects granted to the private sector were evaluated instead. Mainly companies from the Earth and environmental sciences participated followed by the engineering and technology sector (ENG-TECH). Overall, 26% of the private companies participated in more than one TNA call highlighting the successful approach on attracting the private sector. One of the eight companies participating in more than one TNA project was from the ENG-TECH sector, emphasising the potential for expanding the interactions with this sector. In general, there was a small demand for training services by the private companies as most TNAs focussed on the demonstration and improvement of instrumentation so that technical as well as innovation services were mainly requested. Overall, the experience of the private sector with accessing RIs via the TNA program was very positive.

The accessed facilities were valued as a unique resource where a fruitful collaboration with experts allows sharing of knowledge critical for the enhancement of innovations such as prototype instrumentation. The TNA call dedicated to the private sector was appreciated in terms of the higher flexibility of the application, the stronger support by the TNA team, and the shorter duration of the selection process. However, small companies in particular highlighted the amount of documentation needed for the application process and for post-access.

Public authorities were addressed in a set of (two) training webinars. The TNA pilot project for PAs was a large success with almost 150 participants, representing 92 public authorities from 47 (13 non-European) countries around the world. Only about a third had previously participated in an ATMO-ACCESS activity, underlining the importance not only of the high visibility that such events should have in the community of public authorities (e.g. through the WHO newsletter), but also of the appealing, policy-relevant topic to provide insights, knowledge and expertise. This event has given extra visibility and familiarization to the European atmospheric RIs and to the concept of TNA, indicating the importance of these engagement and training webinars for addressing a wider audience and introducing them to RIs and the opportunities which come therewith.

The online format of the engagement event as well as the interaction with 12 expert scientists from 9 RIs on 6 emerging pollutants were highly appreciated by the audience. More than 80% of the respondents to the survey rated the webinar with more than 4 out of 5 satisfaction points. The interest in further webinars was expressed focussing on specific pollutants, highlighting the wish of the PAs for continued TNA opportunities with the research community and facilities beyond ATMO-ACCESS.

All three pilot projects were dominated by the European presence (more than 75%). Nevertheless, among the stakeholders responding to the TNA call for the private sector, some were also based in the United States. On the other hand, Asian, African, and South American public authorities participated in the TNA training webinars organised by T6.4. In general, there is a large potential in engaging non-European countries, as expressed by the relevant users. Needs and priorities in the field of atmospheric science expand beyond European frontiers can therefore be exploited by the European atmospheric research community and infrastructure. The flexibility and innovative nature of access modalities facilitates and optimises access to multiple facilities), and attracts an intercontinental audience, possibly since travel costs are reduced. While the private sector prefers physical access or a combination of physical and remote access, public authorities are reluctant to travel abroad, were attracted to join remotely, and are furthermore interested in a virtual access (including accessing air quality monitoring data). The almost three-year effort to promote TNA access to stakeholders beyond the standard research community has proven challenging. A key challenge has been the definition of the

topic of interaction between access providers and stakeholders, decided through co-design and the exploration of key policy issues impacting particularly public authorities and innovators in technology. Then, the systematic and targeted dissemination of the TNA opportunities places the necessary broad visibility which lack of was found as being the main barrier between stakeholders and ATMO-ACCESS preparatory and co-design activities. However, the standard TNA framework still limits certain stakeholders access to RIs, highlighting the need for tailored TNA programs and innovative access modalities. Procedural barriers, such as bureaucracy and terminology, pose a pressing obstacle to broader stakeholder participation, as expressed by all three stakeholder groups. Overall, the results make a compelling case for a flexible, co-funded access mechanism specifically tailored to the needs of the individual stakeholder type, particularly in contexts where national or institutional funding is insufficient. The findings reinforce the need for institutional backing at the European level to ensure inclusivity, sustainability, and greater impact of RI-based scientific collaboration. Overall, these findings point towards a preferred TNA model that is collaborative, streamlined, and co-funded, while gradually evolving to include open and integrated access models that enhance both operational flexibility and scientific transparency.

6 Conclusions & future recommendations

Three different approaches were chosen for the three TNA pilot projects. International stakeholders, namely ESA and EUMETSAT, were addressed by a complex co-design approach involving the participating RIs and the stakeholders (Section 2.1). The private sector including innovators in technology were attracted by the TNA calls for the private sector and were overall excited about the opportunity to collaborate with RIs and the outcome of the TNA projects, which were mainly innovation-oriented. The Atmobox was introduced as a unique instrumental service, however, the service started late in the project and the uptake was low. Public authorities were contacted through four liaison networks (ACTRIS, RI-URBANS, ICLEI-EU, WHO-BreathLife). In five engagement and co-design events with PAs, their needs were assessed with the result to raise the awareness of ATMO-ACCESS and the TNA concept. Ultimately, a set of training webinars on the revised EU ambient air quality directive were offered as TNA pilot projects (Section 2.3).

The elements presented in this document show that the current standard TNA framework in EU-funded project is not entirely suited for this type of access initiative. Instead, specific access programmes could be developed by RIs for these types of users. This would allow for a more targeted approach.

Such access programmes should take into account the following recommendations:

- **Involve the specific stakeholders in designing and coordinating the access together with the RI**, allowing adjustments and full transparency. In this way the access will become more efficient and will produce higher impact.
- **Increase the transparency of the decision-making process** by updating the access providers about the status of the project at all steps in the process: feasibility, implementation, dissemination of results. This will reduce the risks of subsequent disengagement and will increase predictability. **Allow flexible implementation and reporting, with less bureaucratic procedures.** The stakeholders are result-oriented. Mature RIs should have built sufficient level of trust so that simplified reporting is sufficient to account for the costs. On the other hand, excessive bureaucracy comes with high costs, making the access provision less efficient and for some stakeholders even not feasible.
- **Facilitate access to multiple facilities and combination of access modalities** for these stakeholders as a pre-requisite. Defining the facilities to be accessed already in the application phase is not efficient from the perspective of some stakeholders because it requires knowledge on the existing capacities, and the specific vocabulary. This could be facilitated in the co-designing phase.
- **Accurately define in advance the available budget for access providers**, so that they can more easily commit to participate in such access campaigns/programs
- **Implement a novel framework for long-term implementation.** Services such as the complex Cal/Val program involving international stakeholders necessitate very long timelines for implementation and a high capacity of RIs and access modalities. A specific framework would need to be developed for such services, with involved RIs being committed to contribute in the long term.
- **Encourage user feedback to support assessment of granted access and its impact.** So far, the user feedback has been voluntary, with an average of only ~40% of the users participating in the feedback questionnaire (Petracca Altieri et. al. 2024). Assessing the performance and the success of the TNA is crucial for identifying possible changing needs of stakeholders and possible weaknesses in the TNA program.

In addition, some specific recommendations can be listed concerning the outreach and dissemination aspects: New groups of stakeholders can particularly be attracted by:

- **Raising the awareness of the European Atmospheric Research Infrastructure networks and projects (e.g. ATMO-ACCESS) and the benefits of the TNA opportunities and programs.** Many representatives of PAs were not

aware of such services and potential. Furthermore, few innovators in technology showed interest in the Atmobox, likely due to timing issues and the limited knowledge of this opportunity. Improving outreach was emphasised by all three stakeholder groups.

- **Dedicated knowledge transfer and training programs** for emerging policy-relevant needs, such as the engagement events performed within T6.4, have the potential to contribute to sustained capacity building and long-term impact via access initiatives.
- **Successful collaborations between RIs and stakeholder groups should be actively promoted** to demonstrate tangible value (Rivier et. al. 2023). Conferences are well-suited platforms to showcase TNA and share successful projects with the stakeholder groups. Conferences have already been used during the project for disseminating the successful interactions with, e.g. public authorities (Athanasopoulou et. al. 2025). The international stakeholders projects were disseminated at two EarthCARE Cal/Val workshops: 1st ESA-JAXA EarthCARE In-Orbit Validation Workshop (e.g. Baars (2025)); 2nd ESA-JAXA EarthCARE In-Orbit Validation Workshop (e.g. Baars et. al. (2025) and Nicolae et al. (2025)). In addition, short follow-up interviews or short surveys after the successful access may help demonstrating the value of TNA (Ozolina 2025; Stachlewska u. a. 2024).
- **Extending outreach to non-European countries.** In all three TNA pilot projects, stakeholders were predominantly European. However, there is a large potential for intercontinental collaborations.

Overall, the evaluation of the novel pilot modalities emphasises the need to establish collaborative and co-funded access programs with innovative access modalities, tailored to the needs of the specific stakeholder groups. Flexible TNA modalities are required allowing operational adaptability, reduce bureaucracy, and ensure scientific transparency. In addition, institutional backing at the European level is essential to strengthen service provision to specific stakeholder groups (space agencies, private sector, public authorities) and maximise the benefits of RI-based collaboration, ensuring broader engagement, continuity, and impact.

6 References

- Athanasopoulou, Eleni. 2023. *Proposed TNA pilot for public authorities*. deliverable 6.4. NOA. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2025/01/ATMO-ACCESS_WP6_-D6.4_Proposed-TNA-pilots-for-public-authorities_V3.pdf.
- Athanasopoulou, Eleni, Ariane Dubost, John Wenger, und Sabine Philippin. 2025. *A pilot to showcase the interaction of National public authorities with the European Atmospheric Research Facilities*. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-20393>.
- Baars, Holger. 2025. „First validation results from AECARE including the ATMO ACCESS pilot activity“. Conference paper presented auf 1st ESA-JAXA EarthCARE In-Orbit Validation Workshop. <https://www.earthcare-validation-2025-1.org/final-programme>.
- Baars, Holger, Eleni Marinou, Lucia Mona, u. a. 2025. „An overview of of the European activities for the EarthCARE validation in the framework of ACTRIS/ATMO-ACCESS (EVID05)“. Conference paper presented auf 2nd ESA-JAXA EarthCARE In-Orbit Validation Workshop. <https://www.earthcare-validation-2025-2.org/poster-list-demos>.
- Fuchs, Hendrik, Michelle Färber, Doina Nicolae, Eleni Athanasopoulou, John Wenger, und Leonard Rivier. 2025. *TNA pilots completed and questionnaires issued*. milestone 24. FZJ, INOE, NOA, UCC, CNRS. <https://zenodo.org/records/14983031>.
- Nicolae, Doina. 2025. „The relevance of a GAW regional station for correlative lidar measurements supporting ATLID product validation“. Conference paper presented auf 2nd ESA-JAXA EarthCARE In-Orbit Validation Workshop. <https://www.earthcare-validation-2025-2.org/poster-list-demos>.
- Nicolae, Doina, Rosa Maria Petracca Altieri, und John Wenger. 2023. *Proposed TNA pilot for international stakeholders*. deliverable 6.2. INOE, CNR, UCC. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/09/ATMO-ACCESS_D6.2_M30.pdf.
- Ozolina, Karlina. 2025. *Report on success of the communications actions based on strategies implemented for the pilot access calls, including recommendations and best practices*. deliverable 2.4. ICOS ERIC. <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2025/06/ATMO-ACCESS-D2.4-Report-on-success-of-the-communications-actions-based-on-strategies-implemented-for-the-pilot-access-calls-including-recommendations-and-best-practices.pdf>.
- Petracca Altieri, Rosa Maria, Giuseppe Gargano, Simone Gagliardi, und Carmela Cornacchia. 2021. *Milestone 9.1: Description of application, review and selection process for TNA to ATMO-ACCESS facilities*. milestone 40. CNR. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2021/10/ATMO_ACCESS_WP9_Milestone40.pdf.
- Petracca Altieri, Rosa Maria, Simona Loperte, und Ariane Dubost. 2024. *Report proposing a common access management concept for atmospheric RIs*. deliverable 1.1. CNR. file:///C:/Users/m.farber/Downloads/ATMO-ACCESS_WP1_D1_1_V1_Public%20Under%20EC%20Review.pdf.
- Rivier, Leonard, O. Laurent, S. Sauvage, und R. Petracca. 2023. *Proposed TNA pilot for innovators in technology*. deliverable 6.3. CNRS. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2025/07/ATMO-ACCESS-D6.3_pilots_innovators-in-technology_M52.pdf.

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Stachlewska, Iwona, Dominika Szczepanik, und Ariane Dubost. 2024. *Report on the integrated communication strategies*. milestone 36. UW, CNRS. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/05/ATMO-ACCESS-D2.2.1_vf.pdf.

Wenger, John. 2022. *General design concept for flexible access modalities*. deliverable 6.1. UCC. <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2022/07/ATMO-ACCESS-Deliverable-6.1-M15-vf.pdf>.

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